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Research Article

SPOUSE RIGHT TO MEDICAL PRIVACY¹Kamil M. Arslanov, ²Ayrat R. Davletshin¹Kazan Federal University, Kremlyovskaya St, 18, Kazan, Respublika Tatarstan, Russia, 420008**Abstract**

In society, the family holds a special place among other social institutions. Family relations predetermine both the future of an individual and a whole generation in many respects. Therefore, from a medical point of view, the question of the health of spouses, children, and family as a whole continues to remain relevant.

Premarital medical examination and open communication of the results is now being implemented only on a voluntary basis. Is such an approach able to protect the interests of both spouses and society, and how does it relate to the right of everyone to privacy and family secret?

As part of the work, we studied the experience of foreign countries on the issue of medical examination of spouses and medical privacy of the examination results.

In the domestic scientific literature, it is formed a position on the need for legislative consolidation of the mandatory mutual awareness of spouses regarding the results of a medical examination.

Key words: *Medical privacy, confidentiality, family law, marriage, spouse relations, personal non-property relations, information, medical examination.*

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INTRODUCTION:

The rules and regulations relating to the legal regulation of marriage issues, in conjunction with the medical aspect, require the utmost accuracy and tolerance from the legislator. The issues of personal privacy and intimate life of a person have the right to confidentiality.

On the other hand, we put the interests of the other spouse in ensuring safety and protecting his/her health and life lower than, for example, the interests of the employer, who, when applying for a job, requires such a medical certificate that the personnel department will know more about an employee's health than even the employee himself/herself. Let us explain why we come to such conclusions.

A prerequisite for creating a full-fledged family with healthy children is a medical examination of the persons entering into marriage. Late awareness of future spouses can lead to negative consequences, which has predetermined the introduction of this institution into the family legislation of the Russian Federation.

At the same time, it should be noted that the subjective right of future spouses to pre-marital medical examination is exercised solely on a voluntary basis. To do this, the spouses apply to the health care institutions at the place of residence for the purpose of passing a direct examination or receiving advice on medical and genetic issues [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The presented research is based on the data formulated in the domestic and foreign doctrinal and legislative sources. We used general scientific (logical, system-structural, analytical, synthetic) and private-scientific methods.

In particular, the authors were guided from the point of view of the practical use of medical secrets, applied the methods of instrumental theory of law, the method of legal means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

In accordance with Article 23 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, "everyone has the right to privacy, personal and family secrets, protection of his/her honor and good name" [2]. Taking into account the abovementioned constitutional provisions, the personal rights of each of the examined spouses are guaranteed, in order not to allow the disclosure of intimate issues of private life. Based on the foregoing, the survey results are communicated to the other spouse after obtaining the consent of the person examined. According to Article

15 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation, the information regarding passage and results of the pre-marital medical examination is a medical privacy and can be provided to the other spouse only with the consent of the person examined.

Similar rules are provided for in the foreign law, which, however, sometimes also play a formal role. For example, according to the French Civil Code, a medical certificate shall be submitted by the spouses to the official registering the civil status acts as a guarantor of the information of the spouses, but the results of the medical examination are not reflected in the certificate. On the other hand, Article 18 of the Civil Code of France regulates the possibility of recognizing a marriage as invalid on the basis of "delusion" of one of the spouses regarding the partner's identity or his/her main qualities (sexual and other diseases).

The norm on the medical certificate was born in France in the 19th century, which was a permission to enter into marriage and was expressed by the mark "bon pour le mariage" - "suitable for marriage". That is, the refusal to enter into a marriage for medical reasons took place. In Roman law, suitability for marriage was checked by examination. The list of diseases that interfere with marriage was stipulated by the family legislation of the People's Republic of Bulgaria.

Such rigid norms have sunk into oblivion and have remained a history. In the developed countries, the liberalization of family norms and the strengthening of personal human rights have reached the limit, which was the main occurrence of the self-destructive mechanism.

Citing as an example those norms that, in our opinion, show the importance of the issue being studied, it is worth noting Article 30 of the Family Code of Ukraine [3], which stipulates the obligation for the spouses to inform each other about health status and medical examination results, and the concealment of this information will be the grounds for declaring marriage invalid.

These relations are also strictly regulated by the Family Code of Bulgaria, where Article 9 states: a medical certificate shall be provided upon registration with the registry office. At the same time, Article 7 of the UK Insurance Committee states that the presence of the disease is an obstacle to marriage, with the exception of cases when the other spouse is aware of the disease.

It may be noted family law of the United States of

America, according to which there are a number of diseases that interfere with marriage (determined by each state separately and entered into a special register). If one of the spouses has hidden information about the existing or past diseases, the second has the right to declare the marriage null and void due to the previously mentioned ground of “delusion” at the time of giving consent to marriage.

Italian law has a similar regulation that “a delusion regarding a spouse’s personal qualities occurs, if the spouse challenging the marriage validity would not give consent to the marriage, if it were known to him/her that the other spouse suffered from a physical or mental illness or an anomaly or deviation from sexual issues that impeded family life”.

It should be borne in mind that the Russian law has similar grounds for invalidating a marriage: this is the concealment by one of the spouses of information about a sexually transmitted disease or HIV infection. At the same time, it is necessary to comply with a number of conditions when applying to the court with the requirements to declare a marriage invalid:

- The spouse whose rights were violated, previously, before marriage, did not have the information about the partner’s illness.
- The deadline for filing a claim is one year from the moment when one of the spouses found out or should have known about the hidden disease (Section 4, Article 169 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation, Article 181 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation).

The provisions of Article 15 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation are supplemented by the provisions of Article No. 323-FZ dated November 21, 2011 "On the Basis of the Protection of Public Health in the Russian Federation" [4], which also provides for the right to free advice on family planning, the presence of socially significant diseases and other examinations in medical organizations of the public health system in order to prevent possible hereditary and congenital diseases in the descendants. It should be noted that during the development of the draft Family Code of the Russian Federation, various formulations of the norm of Article 15 were proposed. For example, L.E. Chicherova proposed to formulate Article 15 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation the following edition: "1. Persons entering into marriage shall undergo a medical examination and, if necessary, counseling on medical-genetic and family planning issues, the results of which are necessarily communicated only to the persons who have filed an application for

marriage registration. 2. Hiding a serious illness, as well as a disease that is dangerous for the other spouse and their descendants, is the basis for the marriage to be declared invalid at the request of the other spouse” [5].

O.G. Kurilenko supports this point of view and insists on the approval of the List of Relevant Diseases by the Government of the Russian Federation. “It should be expanded to include the most common severe or contagious chronic diseases that pose a threat to the health of the other spouse or descendants, as well as pathologies precluding normal marital relations” [6]. In addition to sexually transmitted diseases, O.G. Kurylenko proposes to include the inability to have children, the presence of tuberculosis and diabetes as similar grounds for invalidating a marriage.

Speaking about the object of legal relations of persons entering into marriage, it is necessary to note the point of view of E.V. Gordeyuk [7], who believes that legal relationships arise even before marriage. These legal ties relate to intangible benefits, one of which is noted by the author and the right to information about a partner’s health. E.V. Gordeyuk also singles out the rights in the sphere of morality - love and respect, which implies openness and honesty between the persons entering into marriage.

In this regard, it is useful to recall the case of the ECtHR “Kossey versus United Kingdom”, in which judge Z.K. Martens expressed a dissenting opinion [8]. In it, he expressed the position that the essence of marriage is not the ability to have sex and have children. According to Z.K. Martens, marriage is a legal institution within which legal relations between partners, third parties, state arise, and therefore, he believes that marriage is a type of close relationship, and the intellectual, spiritual and emotional connections are no less important than physical ones. But, in this case, the previously stated assumptions are only confirmed - the marriage alliance obliges the spouses to absolute sincerity, and such secrets cannot be a secret for the parties [9]. Thus, the issue of declarativeness of the norm of Article 15 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation, which is debatable in the scientific circles, is also reflected in this aspect.

The alternative method of protecting the violated rights in the form of collecting moral damage is also very interesting. And it arises the question: Is it applicable and sufficient to meet the interests of the affected person?

Arslanov K.M. believes that “the functions of the

legal substitution for compensation for moral damage in the event of an encroachment on honor, dignity, business reputation and privacy are, firstly, "personal satisfaction" of a victim from the violation of a person and, secondly, prevention of new similar violations" [10]. We continue to support this view that it is unacceptable to use the usual for civil law theory of compensation, considering any harm as the arithmetic amount of non-property negative consequences resulting from the violation [11]. Clause 3 of Article 15 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation looks like regulation after the fact in this situation, because in cases of, for example, concealing information about an incurable disease, the health of the other spouse is already endangered. According to the provisions of Articles 27-30 and Article 15 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation, a bona fide spouse will not be able to demand that the marriage be recognized as invalid, since such grounds as, for example, concealing information about a sex change or other significant surgical intervention are not provided for by the current family legislation of the Russian Federation. With this approach, we sacrifice the goals and natural desires of a bona fide spouse to have healthy children [12]. In such a situation, a bona fide spouse has no choice but to exercise the right to divorce, which entails completely different consequences than invalidation of the marriage [13], [14].

According to this discussion topic, there is a point of view of L.N. Bardin, who also believes that "the family is under state protection, and not the right of one family member to conceal from the other family member the result of a medical examination as information dangerous to the health of both spouses and their future children" [15]. Thus, incorrect prioritization violates the rights of the second spouse [16].

CONCLUSIONS:

In the scientific literature, it is formed a position on the need for legislative consolidation of the mandatory mutual awareness of spouses regarding the results of a medical examination. It is necessary to obligate the persons entering into a marriage to notify each other about the presence of diseases threatening human life and health, of sex change surgeries and other significant interventions, as this information may affect the adoption of a conscious decision by the spouses [17], [18].

It should be noted that as far back as 1970, the obligatory pre-marital medical examination was insisted and written by V.P. Chess and B.L. Haskelberg [19], who proposed to extend the ban on

marriage for medical reasons, but the 1995 Family Code implemented a compromise decision on the voluntary nature of a medical examination with strict protection of the medical privacy of each spouse. It is equally interesting the judgments of I.N. Tarusina, who qualifies the concealment by one of the spouses of the fact of sex change during marriage, as a transaction, made under the influence of delusion in the subject (clause 4 of Part 2 of Article 178 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation), or as a deal made under the influence of fraud (paragraph 2 of Part 2 of Article 179 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation) [20].

According to I.B. Novitsky, "the term "delusion" occurs when the person is unintentionally and besides someone's influence makes misconceptions for himself/herself or remains in the dark about certain circumstances..." [21]. Thus, deception is manifested not only in the elements of the transaction, but also in the circumstances accompanying its performance. In our opinion, the proposals made by O.Yu. Ilina are the most compromising as a solution to the problem raised:

- 1) to establish the mandatory medical examination of persons entering into marriage;
- 2) the partners themselves decide to disclose information to each other;
- 3) according to the examination results, in case of detection of HIV infection, a sexually transmitted disease, the patient is warned in writing about criminal liability for the spread and infection of third parties [22].

SUMMARY:

According to the Constitution of the Russian Federation (Article 2), a person, his/her rights and freedoms are the highest value, their recognition, observance and protection is the duty of the state. In this case, according to Article 55 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, they may be limited to the extent necessary to protect the foundations of the constitutional order, morality, health, rights and legitimate interests of others, to ensure the defense of the country and the security of the state.

In our opinion, it is necessary to adjust the provisions of Article 15 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation, adding to it the provisions on mandatory conduct of pre-marital medical examinations and notification of the future spouses of the results.

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